

Marulipi - An Innovative Substitution Cipher

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Introduction:

Marulipi is an innovative cryptographic system that substitutes traditional English characters with geometric shapes. This system, devised by Kamanuru Kiran Kumar, leverages circles, squares, and triangles to represent lowercase letters, uppercase letters, and numerals, respectively. The system's structured approach provides a secure and artistic method for encoding information.

Geometric Representation and Mapping Formulas:

1. Character-to-Shape Mapping Function (C2S):

The function C2S maps each character from the English alphabet and numerals to a unique geometric shape.

$$C2S(x) = \begin{cases} \text{Shape}_y & \text{if } x \in \text{lowercase letters (a-z)} \\ \text{Shape}_y & \text{if } x \in \text{uppercase letters (A-Z)} \\ \text{Shape}_y & \text{if } x \in \text{numerals (0-9)} \end{cases}$$

Each Shape_y corresponds to a specific geometric figure, such as a full circle, half-circle, quarter-square, or triangle.

2. Position Mapping and Transformation (PMT):

This function adjusts the position or orientation of a shape to encode additional information, such as variations in the represented character or to indicate a special encoding mode.

$$PMT(\text{Shape}_y, \theta) = \text{Shape}_{y'}$$

Where θ represents the rotation angle. For example, a rotation by 90° could differentiate between two characters that otherwise use the same base shape.

3. Composite Shape Encoding (CSE):

In cases where a combination of shapes is used to represent a single character or a set of characters, CSE defines the rules for combining these shapes.

$$CSE(C2S(x_1), C2S(x_2), \dots, C2S(x_n)) = \text{CompositeShape}$$

This function can create complex symbols by combining basic shapes, providing a method for encoding multiple characters or special sequences.

4. Shape and Component Differentiation:

Each shape can be divided into components (e.g., full, half, quarter) to further differentiate characters. For instance, a circle could be divided into:

- Full circle (C_0)
- Half-circle ($C_{1/2}$)
- Quarter-circle ($C_{1/4}$)

The notation $C2S(x) = C_i$ indicates that the character x maps to the i -th component of the circle shape.

Decoding Mechanism:

1. Shape-to-Character Mapping Function (S2C):

This function reverses the character-to-shape mapping, converting geometric shapes back into their corresponding characters.

$$S2C(\text{Shape}_y) = x$$

Where Shape_y is the geometric representation, and x is the decoded character.

2. Inverse Position Mapping and Transformation (IPMT):

The IPMT function undoes any transformations applied during encoding, such as rotations.

$$IPMT(\text{Shape}_y, -\theta) = \text{Shape}_y$$

This function restores the original orientation or position of the shape.

3. Decompose Shape Decoding (DCD):

When composite shapes are used, DCD is employed to decompose the shapes into their constituent characters.

$$DCD(\text{CompositeShape}) = (C2S(x_1), C2S(x_2), \dots, C2S(x_n))$$

Error Correction and Detection:

To enhance the reliability of Marulipi, error correction and detection mechanisms can be incorporated. These mechanisms may include:

1. Checksum Calculation:

A checksum can be computed for a sequence of encoded shapes to verify data integrity.

$$\text{Checksum} = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{Shape}_i \pmod{m}$$

Where n is the number of shapes and m is a predefined modulus.

2. Parity Bit Addition:

For each shape, a parity bit can be added to indicate the parity (even or odd) of the character's position in the encoding sequence.

3. Redundancy Bits:

Additional bits can be added to the encoded data to allow for error detection and correction, similar to Hamming codes.

Applications and Implications:

Marulipi's unique geometric encoding method provides a secure communication medium, particularly in contexts where visual or artistic representation is valuable. Its potential applications extend to secure messaging, artistic endeavors, and educational tools for teaching cryptography and data encoding.

Challenges and Limitations:

The precision required for shape reproduction can be a limitation, particularly in handwritten contexts. Furthermore, as a substitution cipher, Marulipi may be vulnerable to cryptographic attacks if the mapping between characters and shapes is exposed.

Future Directions:

Future research could focus on optimizing the encoding process, developing automated tools for encoding and decoding, and exploring the integration of Marulipi with other cryptographic systems to enhance security. There is also potential for adapting Marulipi to different languages and scripts, broadening its applicability.

Conclusion:

Kamanuru Kiran Kumar's Marulipi cipher represents a novel contribution to cryptography. By utilizing geometric shapes, it offers a distinctive and visually appealing alternative script for English. This thesis provides an in-depth exploration of Marulipi's structure, mathematical foundations, and potential applications, highlighting its relevance in secure communication and beyond.